

Spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) by adsorption of its 1-allyl-3-(6-methylpyridyl)thiourea complex on polyurethane foam

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A spectrophotometric method for the determination of copper(II) after adsorption of its 1-allyl-3-(6-methylpyridyl)thiourea complex on polyurethane foam is discussed. The method has been applied to the determination of copper(II) in alloy samples.

Pyridyl and substituted pyridyl thioureas have been investigated as organic reagents for copper. These compounds react with many cations and anions to give colour reactions of analytical importance. The presence of three coordinating groups, two amino and one thiocarbonyl in thiourea leads the formation of polynuclear complexes¹ where amino group acts as a bridging unit. There are several spectrophotometric methods for the determination of copper(II)². The present paper describes a new method based on adsorption of newly synthesized copper(II)-1-allyl-3-(6-methylpyridyl)thiourea (AMPT) complex on polyurethane foam (commercial U-foam) and subsequent determination of copper(II) spectrophotometrically. The polyurethane foam can be re-used.

The use of polyurethane foam as an adsorbent in 'solid-liquid extraction' technique as modified by Bowen³ offers low solubility of the extractant, easy use of large phase ratios, easy separation of phases and a synergistic extraction effect unlike that in liquid-liquid extraction.

Results and Discussion

The Cu^{II} complex showed maximum absorbance at 490 nm at pH 2.5 using 0.2% reagent solution (2.5 ml), six polyurethane foam pieces and buffer solution (3 ml). The system obeyed Beer's law in the range 12–110 µg of Cu^{II}. The sensitivity of the reaction was found to be 0.015 µg cm² of Cu^{II} for 0.001 absorbance and molar absorptivity 1.62 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The effect of diverse ions in the determination of 80 µg of Cu^{II} showed the following tolerance limits (µg, in parenthesis) : Ag^I (90), Mg^{II} (120), Ni^{II} (110), Co^{II} (150), Zn^{II} (160), Fe^{III} (130), Pt^{IV} (180), V^V (75), U^{VI} (140).

Application : A sample of Monel wire/Brass sample (No

41.2; 0.1 g) was dissolved in aqua regia, then evaporated to dryness and the oxides of nitrogen were expelled by treatment with HCl. The residue was extracted with water and diluted to 100 ml. An appropriate aliquot was taken, its pH adjusted to 2.5 and Cu^{II} determined spectrophotometrically by the general procedure. The results were found to be in good agreement with the certified values (Table 1).

Table 1. Determination of copper(II) in Monel wire and brass sample

Sample	Certified(%)	Amount of Cu ^{II} composition (%)	Amount of Cu ^{II} taken (µg)	Average (µg) (error%)
Monel wire	Ni	66.24	69.55	
	Cu	31.18	70.12	69.98
	Fe	1.18	71.21	(-0.03121)
	Mn	1.08	68.92	
	Mg	0.093	70.09	
	Al	0.093		
	Si	0.083		
	C	0.083		
Brass sample	S	0.037		
	Cu	58.18	80.56	
	Pb	2.56	79.62	80.10
	Zn	38.99	79.55	(+0.1204)
	Fe	0.09	80.32	
Sn	0.12	80.48		

Experimental

1-Allyl-3-(6-methylpyridyl)thiourea was synthesized by reacting equimolar quantities of 6-methyl-2-aminopyridine and allyl isothiocyanate. A standard stock solution of Cu^{II} (1000 ppm) was prepared from copper foil. A 0.2% solution of the reagent was prepared in ethanol. Acetate buffer (pH 2–5) was prepared by mixing equal volume of 1 M acetic acid and 1 M ammonium acetate.

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. A Chemito UV-VIS-2000 spectrophotometer and a Systronics 335 pH meter were used.

Polyurethane foam (commercially U-foam) pieces (1 cm³ size) were prepared by the reported method⁴. Foam pieces were soaked in 1 M HCl for ~10 h to remove possible inorganic contaminants, then rinsed with distilled water, squeezed and dried in air before use.

Procedure : To an aliquot of sample solution containing 80 µg of Cu^{II} were added 0.2% of AMPT solution (3.0 ml) and acetate buffer (3.0 ml; pH 2.5). The mixture was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and allowed to stand for a few minutes to ensure complete colour formation to light yellow. To the Cu^{II}-AMPT complex so formed, six foam pieces were added and shaken vigorously to enable the complete adsorption of the metal complex on foam pieces. After adsorption the colour changed to pale yellow. The foam pieces were then squeezed completely with

chloroform (2 × 5 ml). Traces of water were removed by adding anhydrous sodium sulfate. After complete extraction the absorbance of the solution was measured at 490 nm against reagent blank. The metal was estimated from a pre-calibrated graph.

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